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ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ СТУДЕНТОВ НЕФТЕГАЗОВОГО ПРОФИЛЯ** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7458527>**АННОТАЦИЯ**

На данный момент появляется все больше литературных свидетельств создания механизма обратной связи в высшем образовании. Оценка знаний учащихся является неотъемлемой частью обучения. Учащиеся часто недовольны стандартными моделями предоставления обратной связи, и их восприятие часто не совпадает с мнением учителей, которые считают, что учащиеся могут недооценивать обратную связь. Стандартное оценивание, как правило, дает ограниченную информацию, которая фокусируется на оценивании и только, не вовлекая учащихся в процесс обучения. В данной статье дается краткий обзор использования суммативного оценивания в обучении студентов нефтегазового профиля. Собственно, исследование основано на идее о том, что современные педагогические технологии, внедряемые в настоящее время, более эффективны и стимулирующие, чем прежние методы преподавания. В этом исследовании изучалась обоснованность использования викторин как формы итоговой оценки вместо экзамена или опросников. Уровень владения английским языком участниками, на котором проводилось данное исследование, был средним в университете по нефтегазовому профилю, где рекомендуемая учебная программа предъявляет повышенные требования к развитию словарного запаса. Результаты данного исследования показали, что оценивание играет немаловажную роль и может мотивировать студентов изучению английского языка. Результаты этого исследования также будут использованы в качестве основы, на которой могут быть сделаны конкретные предложения по практическому применению оценивания в повседневной аудитории.

Ключевые слова: обратная связь, формирующая, суммативная, оценка, мотивация, викторина, вопросник, подход.

Razikova D.S.Branch of Russian state university of oil
and gas (NRU) in Tashkent, teacher**USE OF QUIZES AS A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT IN TEACHING STUDENTS OF AN
OIL AND GAS PROFILE****ANNOTATION**

At the moment there is an increasing literary evidence for the design of feedback in higher education. The role of assessing the students' knowledge is an essential part in teaching. Students are often dissatisfied with standard models of giving feedback and their perceptions often do not align

with that of teachers who feel that students may undervalue the feedback. Standard feedback tends to give limited information that focuses on the assessment product and does not engage students in learning processes. This article gives a brief outline of using summative assessment in teaching the oil and gas profile students. Actually the research is based on the idea that modern pedagogical technologies implemented nowadays are more effective and motivational than the previous methods of teaching. This research investigated the validity of using the quizzes as a form of summative assessment, instead taking an exam or questionnaires. The participants' level of knowledge of English, in which this research was conducted, was intermediate at the University specialized in oil and gas profile, where greater demands are imposed on developing vocabulary skills by the recommended curriculum. The results of this research revealed that the role of assessment is indispensable and it has an ability to motivate students to learn English. The results of this research will also be used as a basis upon which specific suggestions for the practical implementation of assessment in the everyday classroom can be made.

Key words: feedback, formative, summative, assessment, motivate, quiz, questionnaire, approach.

Razikova D.S.

Rossiya davlat neft va gaz universiteti
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NEFT VA GAZ YO'NALISHIDAGI TALABALARINI O'QITISHDA SUMMATIV BAHOLASHDAN FOYDALANISH

ANNOTASIYA

Hozirgi vaqtda oliy ta'limda qayta aloqa mexanizmi yaratilganligi haqida adabiyotlar ko'payib bormoqda. O'quvchilar bilimni baholash o'qitishning ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi. Talabalar ko'pincha fikr-mulohazalarni taqdim yetishning standart modellaridan norozi bo'lishadi va ko'pincha o'quvchilar o'z fikr-mulohazalari bo'yicha ularni kam baholashlari mumkin deb hisoblaydigan o'qituvchilarning fikriga zid keladi. Standart baholash odatdagi baholashga qaratilgan cheklangan ma'lumotlarni taqdim etadi va faqat talabalarni o'quv jarayoniga jalb qila olmaydi. Ushbu maqolada neft va gaz sohasida tahsil olayotgan talabalarni o'qitishda summativ baholashdan foydalanish haqida qisqacha tavsifi berilgan. Darhaqiqat, tadqiqot hozirgi kunda joriy etilayotgan zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar avvalgi o'qitish usullariga nisbatan samaraliroq va rag'batlantiruvchi ekanligiga asoslanadi. Ushbu tadqiqot imtihon yoki anketa o'rniga yakuniy baholash shakli sifatida viktorinalardan foydalanishning asosli ekanligini o'rganib chiqdi. Ushbu tadqiqot ishtirokchilarining ingliz tilini bilish darajasi o'rta darajada bo'lib, neft va gaz sohasida o'qiyotganlarga tavsiya etilgan o'quv dasturiga muvofiq so'z boyligini rivojlantirishga yuqori talablar qo'yiladi. Ushbu tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, baholashning o'rni katta va talabalarning ingliz tilini o'rganishga undash salohiyati yuksak. Ushbu tajriba natijalari, shuningdek, kundalik sinfda baholashni amalda qo'llash bo'yicha aniq takliflar kiritilishi mumkin bo'lgan asos sifatida ishlatiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: fikr-mulohaza, formativ, summativ, baholash, motivatsiya, viktorina, anketa, yondashuv.

Assessment is the process of gathering and discussing information from multiple and diverse sources in order to develop a deep understanding of what students know, understand, and can do with their knowledge as a result of their educational experiences; the process culminates when assessment results are used to improve subsequent learning. [1,c.8]. Assessment gives teachers an opportunity to observe the student's progress towards achieving learning objectives, and this can be realized in a variety of ways. **Formative assessment is considered as an effective tool for** monitoring student learning, as it helps students to identify their strengths and weaknesses and target areas that need work, simultaneously it provides with the ongoing feedback that can be used by instructors to improve their teaching and by students to improve their learning gaps. In addition, it can include students assessing themselves, peers, or even the instructor, through writing, quizzes, conversation, and more.

In short, formative assessment occurs throughout a class or course, and seeks to improve student achievement of learning objectives through approaches that can support specific student needs. [2,c.151]. On the contrary, summative assessment evaluates student learning, knowledge, proficiency, or success at the conclusion of an instructional period, like a unit, course, or program. Summative assessment can be used to great effect in conjunction and alignment with formative assessment, and instructors can consider a variety of ways to combine these approaches. It should be admitted, that summative assessment is more complicated and important than the formative one, as it is an evaluation of student learning, skill acquisition, and academic achievement at the conclusion of a defined instructional period, such as a unit, project, course, semester, program, or academic year. Michael Scriven claims that while all assessment techniques can be summative, only some are formative. **In general, formative assessments are quizzes and tests that evaluate how someone is learning a material throughout a course. While summative assessments are quizzes and tests that evaluate how much someone has learned throughout a course.** [3,c. 39-83] There are several types of summative assessment mentioned, some of these are:

- Teacher-designed quizzes and tests that include short essays, multiple-choice questions, short answers, matching activities and fill in the blanks.
- Writing and analytical skills are tested through research papers, media reviews, articles, essays or portfolio.
- Descriptive presentations for various audiences can include role play, group discussions, debates or contests, interactive tasks and activities.
- Oral Assessments - getting students to give speeches, which give students detailed, peer feedback and intended to show off their understanding of a topic.
- Half-yearly, mid-term and end-of-term exams.
- Unit tests or chapter tests unit tests or chapter tests.

Thus, one of the advantages of using summative evaluation is to identify gaps both in learning and teaching, giving valuable insights on students' performance during a semester.

Having explored various approaches for assessing of the learner and having a data about learning outcomes, I have recently used summative assessment to produce a lesson: "How do you know oil and gas industry?" It was performed at the end of the first semester, which included multileveled integrated skills, instead of standardized test. The prevailing concept of my final lesson was to make a research with the purpose to use the results to help prepare students for future administrations of the test and to evaluate their progress. The lecture was in the form of contest, it was intentionally designed in this form in order to attract students' attention without making them worry about final exams. I tried to adopt some materials according to concrete students studying in my group, because of their skills and abilities. This model was chosen as an efficient one, so all the students of the group took an active part. At the lesson I decided to cover various aims, like educational, developing and socio – cultural. Educational aim consisted of revising and fulfilling the gaps in vocabulary of oil and gas profile, classifying them according to their categories, getting acquainted with their special meaning in the technical context. Developing aim was in carrying out several tasks, answering the questions, promoting their skills and abilities, investigating, analyzing and maintaining students to work in group. Socio-cultural aim contained introducing the learners with the collocations used in oil and gas industry and phrases reflecting Englishmen's outlook for this matter. At the end of the lesson:

- Students were able to identify the names of equipment, methods of drilling and tools for performing this process.
- Students found out about the history of oil and gas industry and petroleum engineering.
- Students could pronounce multisyllabic words, translate the glossary of special terms properly.

Before the beginning of the lesson I prepared my classroom and monitor. The students were divided into two groups according to the rule of the contest. My lesson consisted of four parts, in which the first part was devoted to several activities, especially the warm up activities, such as greeting, introducing teams and the rules. This was the first step towards their engagement and causing their interest which was reached successfully. I tried to create positive learning

environment. The next step was revising the previous lesson, by brainstorming the terms. The right answer gave them scores.

In the second part, I introduced the participants with the rules by presenting them slides. But before it I used the pre task activity in video format. While watching the video, they listened to the pronunciation of the active vocabulary, had an image of three sectors in oil and gas industry. After, they tried to classify activities and methods, performed in the industry into three main segments by testing in “Kahoot” platform. Then they checked and discussed their answers. They saw their scores. By observing the whole process in the video, they got acquainted with some new terms denoting oil business. For every right answer each team got a score and at the end this was calculated. Gathering a lot of points encouraged them, this made them act together, collaborating in order to achieve the major purpose. They tried to catch every detail in order not to fail the quiz.

In the third part, I focused on strengthening the skills and strategies what the students learned, which included practicing variety of multi leveled tasks taught during the lesson. In power point multimedia presentation they saw the table and chose the question they preferred. The image was accompanied with the sound effect taken from the famous game “My game”. They were asked to call the names of companies or countries which produce hydrocarbons. It was provoking task, because they saw only the signs, small elements of the picture. They fulfilled the task with enthusiasm. In addition, the learners were given some assignments covering the main purposes of the agenda. Participants of the contest coped with an unexpected challenge very well.

In the end, they were asked “true or false” questions to reflect what they had learned during the semester. They were marked and soon they counted total number of marks in order to get the certificates of achievement. Everybody took an active part both in groups and individually. The aim of the lesson was achieved.

Analyzing the lesson I conducted, I can call three criteria, according to which I designed my lesson: how student centered it was; how inclusive it was; and if I encouraged deep or surface approach to learning. The first thing I would like to mention, is that I chose the quiz-contest type of the lesson themed to petroleum industry in order to monitor the students’ gained knowledge during the semester, to think critically, to work in groups. Providing them sufficient platform to work, I almost did not take part in the game. I was in the role of an instructor. I facilitate them to work, to cope with the tasks. The next step was in that, I did not choose advanced tasks for assignment. Validity and transparency of the given tasks maintained them to create, investigate and think. I did not want to interrupt them while they were answering. I used mild voice, prompted some words, but at the same time I was not in the center, I stepped aside. They decided what to do next. The tasks were not complicated enough, but at the same time they covered needed data. The aim of the lesson was providing the students with the information about their future profession and the business where they intended to work later. The time management was not counted, as a result the lesson lasted a little bit longer, than it was planned. Grammar was checked while the participants were answering to the questions and spoke about their teams, active vocabulary, assessment were done in a proper way which were the best reflectors of mastering learning outcomes. To evaluate students understanding I conducted the summative assessment.

Summing up my narrative, I can say that the lesson was informative. By the end of the lesson all the purposes were achieved.

1. The learners demonstrated creative thinking skills.
2. Worked in groups by taking the decisions.
3. Were able to speak and discuss the vocabulary expressing the oil and gas sphere.
4. The knowledge of students was checked, evaluated and analysed.

While creating the tasks I considered their level of difficulty, validity and student engagement. The assessed tasks that I produced can be evaluated by these criteria: inclusivity and student centeredness. First of all I promoted the pre assessment activity by providing the learners with the basic data used in this subject. The secondly, I arranged the assignments in an extraordinary way so that they could analyze them, and only after that they could answer.

The tasks were designed in the form of working with team. They stayed involved till the end of the lesson. As a result it motivated them to work harder, to think, to investigate and to choose the sufficient answer. And the last point is that they were provided with a constructive feedback according to their interpretation.

References:

1. Huba & Freed: Learner - Centered Assessment on College Campuses: shifting the focus from teaching to learning./2000.- 8.c.
2. Theall, M. and Franklin J.L. - Assessing Teaching Practices and Effectiveness for Formative Purposes. In: A Guide to Faculty Development./ KJ Gillespie and DL Robertson (Eds). Jossey Bass: San Francisco, CA., 2010, 151.c.
3. R. W. Tyler, R. M. Gagne, & M. Scriven - "The methodology of evaluation"/ Perspectives of curriculum evaluation. Chicago, IL: Rand McNally. 1967? 39-83c.

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